

Effect of Soil Toxicity on the Growth and Development of Crimson Clover (*Trifolium incarnatum L.*) and Blue Alfalfa (*Medicago sativa L.*)

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Abstract

A vegetation trial was conducted to test, establish and compare the abilities of crimson clover (*Trifolium incarnatum L.*) and blue alfalfa (*Medicago sativa L.*) to grow, sequester arsenic and improve microbial soil status in soils with deteriorated water and physical properties and with naturally and technogenically reached toxic levels of arsenic. The experiment is based on cultivation of two types of legume crops under the same controlled climatic conditions, but in different soil environments. Contaminated Regosols and control uncontaminated Rhodic Cambisols, Chromic-Calcaric Cambisols and Fluvisols, collected from four geographical points, distributed (4 kg.) in a total of 24 pots/samples and sown with the two investigated crops (2x12) were included in the study. Crop growth and development were monitored during the vegetative and reproductive phenological phases, taking timely biometric measurements. According to the observations made and the results obtained, the crimson clover (*Trifolium incarnatum L.*) is suitable for remediation and improvement of the agrochemical, biological, physical and physicochemical properties of arsenic-contaminated soils - Regosols, by forming a dense root system with a relative abundance of tubers of symbiotic nitrogen-fixing microorganisms in it, in conditions of Interventional contents of arsenic, significant compaction and deteriorated water permeability of the soils. Contamination with arsenic (in association with a number of heavy metals) suppresses the germination of both crops - crimson clover and alfalfa, vegetative phenophases, nutrition, growth and development of clover, but not the fertility of the obtained crop of the studied crops. The main factors limiting the fertility of the two crops in the experiment were the low content of soil colloids (humus and clay) and the poorer soil microbiome. The observed better adaptability in feeding alfalfa in contaminated soils allows this crop to be applied in longer-term remediation measures.

Keywords: crimson clover, alfalfa, arsenic, phytoremediation, Cambisols, Regosols, Fluvisols

Introduction

Arsenic and lead contamination of industrial and agricultural lands around the former Kremikovtzi metallurgical plant (near Sofia, Bulgaria) has been studied and documented for decades (Boyajiev et al., 1985; Tchuldjian et al., 1991; Faitondjiev et al. al., 2000; Atanassova, Doichinova, 2003; Shulin et al., 2004, etc.). According to recent soil-genetic studies, which are

unique for the territory of the combine, the nature of the soil-forming rocks, supplemented by long-term human and technogenic influence, plays a role in the exceeded values of a number of metals and metalloids (Stoykova, 2021).

The area of the former MP "Kremikovtsi" is located on a flat-hilly terrain within the foothills of the Sofia valley. The soil-forming proluvial and colluvial rocks contain redeposited material and fragments of a colorful palette of rock varieties, that make up the adjacent mountain slopes - carbonate rocks, argillites, siltstones, lydrites mixed with ore from the Buhov uranium deposit, fragments of rock formations of the very rare potassium-alkaline magmatic series of the Buhovo-Seslavtsi pluton (mainly syenites) and rock material from the Kremikovtsi barite-iron ore deposit (Dyulgerov, 2005; Angelov et al., 2008, Kalaydzhev, 1993). These natural factors presuppose relatively higher background values for a number of chemical elements - heavy metals and metalloids (including As) and lead to the need for sustainable management of soils and lands.

Soil Science has postulated the ability of legumes, thanks to their symbiotic root-dwelling nitrogen-fixing bacterial species, to increase soil fertility by increasing soil nitrogen, and in addition, there is evidence of arsenic-tolerant and even arsenic-transforming nitrogen-fixing bacterial species (Reichman, 2007, Laha et al. 2021). The cited studies allow us to assume that species and strains with similar properties could also be present in the particular region we studied, especially judging by our data, according to which the behavior of As and its related metalloids Se, Te and Sb is the same. Downward removal from the profile and concentration below 200 cm in the B_{Ck} horizon is observed only in an uncontaminated control profile, adjacent to which is one of the current control profiles for this study. In all the other 6 technogenically polluted profiles of the cited study, where microbial activity was not detected, these four elements are mainly concentrated in the surface soil horizons, where in places they reach upper limits of 111.01 - 409.34 mg/kg (Stoykova et al., 2022).

In world practice, the crimson clover (*Trifolium incarnatum* L.) has been studied as an arsenic accumulator (Bekuzarova et al., 2018, 2019). For alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.), there are a number of studies on an increase in the tissue content of arsenic in contaminated fields (Khattak et al., 1991, Rötting et al., 2013).

Based on the arguments advanced and conclusions drawn, the present study aims to test, establish and compare the abilities of two legume crops (crimson clover and blue alfalfa) to grow, extract arsenic and improve microbial soil status in a vegetation experiment applied on soils with naturally and technogenically reached toxic levels of this pollutant.

Materials and Methods

To achieve the set aims, based on preliminary publicly available official data (PCSRS of SM, 2021), four sampling points were determined from the most common soil types in the area -

Cinnamon forest (Rhodic-Chromic Cambisols), Deluvial soils (Fluvisols) and Regosols (Teoharov et al., 2019; IUSS Working Group WRB., 2022), the latter also classified as Deluvial soils in the used official sources. Accordingly, polluted and non-polluted areas were selected from the soil types (Figure 1). Thus, initially Point 1/Yana and Point 2/ Rudinata were selected as technogenically polluted (respectively,

Figure 1. Geographical location of the studied soils

Regosols and Cambisols), and Point 3/Seslavtsi and Point 4/Kremikovtsi as genetically preserved unpolluted (respectively, Cambisols and Fluvisols).

From each of the four points, in dry winter conditions, on 27/02/2023, 30 kg of soil was collected from horizon A (0-20 cm) of the soil profiles. On the next day, 28/02/2023, the soil was divided into six pots for each of the four study points, each filled with 4 kg of soil and sown in greenhouse conditions with the two crops, each crop in three pots, for statistical reliability of the experiment - a total of 24 pots/samples (8x3 variants) (Figure 2). The crimson clover is the Heuser'S Ostaat variety and the alfalfa is the Gea variety. The seeding rate for both crops is 2 kg/dka (20 mg/100 cm²) or 60 mg/ 300 cm² (3 dm²), which is the approximate area of a pot with a diameter of 20 cm (UC SAREP, 2012; Kirilov, 2016). The initial irrigation rate is 200 ml. every three days (average 70 ml/1 day) for all crops, at an average daily air temperature for the month of March of 7.1°C (-4.8°C - 21.2°C) according to NIMH (National Institute of Meteorology and Hydrology, Bulgaria). Growth and development of cultivated crops were monitored during the vegetative and reproductive phenophases, taking timely biometric measurements (Guertin et al., 2017; Young-Mathews, 2013; GPO, 1960; Kirilov, 2016). As the vegetation progressed, due to a difference in the accumulated biomass and correspondingly greater transpiration, in the mass phase of the second triple leaf (19/04/2023), based on measuring the differences in the weight of the pots for one day, an irrigation rate was determined from 300 ml. every two days (150 ml/1 day) for Regosols and Fluvisols - crops and 500 ml. every two days (250 ml/1 day) for the Cambisols-crops, at an average daily temperature for April of 9°C (-1.7°C - 21.1°C) according to NIMH data. In the phase of inflorescence formation (or bud stage) of the first plant individuals for the entire experiment

Figure 2. Schematic of the vegetation experiment

(20/05/2023), all the pots were taken outside, as close as possible to the natural climatic conditions, and the irrigation rates were determined in a timely manner, according to the amount of precipitation, atmospheric temperature,

phytometric indicators and crop transpiration.

On 15/06/2023, the crops grown on Cambisols were collected, and on 22/06/2023 - the crops grown on Regosols and Fluvisols. At this point, the clover in all variants is in an advanced phase of flowering, while this phase in the alfalfa grown on Cambisols is only reached by a few plant individuals. The plant mass was collected by cutting the plants about 2 cm above the root collar, the clover flower was separated from the plants, the resulting biomass was weighed fresh, dried at 60°C to air-dry state, crushed and quartered several times about 2 g of dry matter from each sample were separated and crushed for testing the arsenic content. The total number of samples obtained was 36 - 12 pieces of alfalfa (stems and leaves), 12 pieces of clover (stems and leaves) and 12 pieces of clover flower.

In order to trace the entire vegetation cycle of the plants, three plant individuals were left in each variant pot.

In the laboratories of the Institute of Soil Science, Agrotechnology and Plant Protection "N. Pushkarov" soil samples were tested for:

- pH - potentiometric
- C - Turin method
- mechanical composition - pyrophosphate method

- total carbonates - Scheibler's method
- As - ISO 11466.

Additional samples were taken from the same four sampling points to study the microbiological composition of the soils subject to the vegetation experiment.

Results and Discussion

The results for the mechanical composition and agrochemical properties of the studied soils are presented in Table 1. According to them, these are light and medium sandy-clay soils with slightly acidic to very slightly alkaline (6.6 - 7.3) pH reaction in water. The highest humus content is Rhodic Cambisols from Point 3 - 4.78 %, followed by Chromic-Calcaric Cambisols from Point 2, Regosols (Toxic) from Point 1 and Fluvisols (from Point 4). The deteriorated water permeability of Regosols and Fluvisols, a result of the low content of the finest fractions and, accordingly, the deteriorated structure of these soils is an important factor that has a significant impact on the development of the studied crops in the current vegetation experience.

Table 1. Arsenic content and basic physical and physicochemical properties of the studied soils

Point No.	Soil Type	pH	C	Carbonates	Hygroscopic Moisture	Fine sand	Silt	Clay	Sum	As	
		H2O				0.25-0.05	0.01-0.005				
			%								
Point 1/Yana	Eutric Regosols (Toxic)	7.3	3.25	0.98	2.3	33.4	17.2	3.4	22.6	86.8	
Point 2/Rudinata	Chromic-Calcaric Cambisols	7.2	3.73	6.56	4.11	35	22.9	6.7	35	14.8	
Point 3/Seslavtsi	Rhodic Cambisols	6.6	4.78	-	3.76	23.7	14.1	11.2	31.6	20.6	
Point 4/Kremikovtsi	Eutric Fluvisols (Arenic)	7.3	1.98	0.63	1.56	37	12.6	4.1	17.9	7.5	

According to the results obtained for arsenic content, toxic levels of metalloid were measured in Regosols (Toxic) from Point 1/Yana. The measured value is 86.8 mg/kg, which is practically within the Intervention norm of 90 mg/kg introduced in Ordinance No. 3/ 01.08.2008. In the control profile of Fluvisols from Point 4/Kremikovtsi, the content is minimal - 7 mg/kg, and in the studied Cambisols, contrary to expectations, the arsenic content is slightly higher in the previously designated as control Point 3/Seslavtsi - 20.6 mg/ kg, compared to the previously declared contaminated, Point 2/Rudinata (14.8 mg.kg), where according to official data based on a 2004 study (Shulin et al., 2004), the metalloid content was tens or even hundreds of mg/kg in the particular locality. After analyzing the properties of this particular soil profile (Point 2), its differences stand out - a high content of carbonates - 6.56 %, a high content of fine sand fraction - 35 % and a distinct maximum content of medium dust fraction - 22.9 %, the latter also affecting the maximum value of the physical clay in this soil sample - 35%, compared to the other 3 studied soils. The question of the reasons for this significant deviation from the preliminary data is debatable. The reasons can be different - biological and pedochemical, but most likely all of them are influenced by the

Figure 3. Single pot/samples of the eight variants studied. Plants are in mass simple leaf phase and beginning of first triple leaf phase for Cambisols - crops, 03/31/2023.

termination of the activity of the metallurgical plant and the improvement of the qualities of the local microclimate and landscape.

The vegetation experiment, involving the cultivation of two types of legume crops under the same controlled climatic conditions, but in different soil environments, gave many and divergent results, both for the phenological development of the crops and for their difficulties in growing in the individual soil types. The main difference between the two crops is the length of their growing cycle. Alfalfa is a perennial and the specific type of clover is an annual crop, but their phenophases, like leguminous grasses, are identical (Kirilov, 2016; Lloveras et al., 2001; Young-Mathews, 2013). In our experiment, this difference became noticeable at the beginning of the reproductive period (phenophase of inflorescence formation or bud stage), which in alfalfa in all soil types occurred about twenty days later than crimson clover.

The experiment was carried out on February 28, 2023. The germination phase, manifested by the appearance of cotyledons above the soil surface (GPO, 1960), was delayed by about ten days

Figure 5. Top - Crops grown in the third and fourth trifoliate phase. A - Regosols (Toxic), B - Chromic-Calcaric Cambisols, C - Rhodic Cambisols, D - Fluvisols.

Below - Deviations from growth norms - yellowing and closing of clover leaves, 05/05/2023.

structure and agrochemical properties of the two coarser soil types - Regosols and Fluvisols, affected such that the onset of the early phenophases in clover was delayed, but its biometric indicators were not deteriorated (Figure 4, Table 2 - dimensions and yield), in compared to alfalfa. At the end of the experiment, this trend also affects the average yield in fresh and air dry weight, which is greater in clover (Table 2). The more active growth of clover is accompanied (in Regosols, Fluvisols and to a lesser extent in Chromic-Calcaric Cambisols) by yellow-green coloring of the

Figure 4. Comparison table, with representative plants from each tested sample/pot, in the third triple leaf phase, with the exception of clover in Regosols and Fluvisols, which is mostly in the second triple leaf phase, 26/04/2023.

for the crops of both crops sown on Regosols (Toxic) - 16 - 18/03/2023, occurring around 7 - 9/03/2023 for

crops of Cambisols and Fluvisols. Germination was suppressed and measured plant density in contaminated Regosols averaged 60 plants/3 sq.m., compared to about 200 in Fluvisols and Chromic-Calcaric Cambisols and over 250 in Rhodic Cambisols (Figure 3). Due to the higher content of humus in Regosols (Toxic) - 3.25 %, the plants manage to gradually synchronize their phases with those of the crops of Fluvisols, which soils in turn have the lowest humus content - 1.98 %.

A general tendency was observed for clover in all soil variants, in the same (Cambisols) or different (Regosols and Fluvisols) phase of development, to have better biometric indicators, compared to those of alfalfa. The deteriorated

leaves, even in the simple leaf phase - a sign of nitrogen deficiency, and in the third and fourth phase trifoliolate and with characteristic leaf closure (UC SAREP, 2012; Stanchev et al., 1984) (Figure 5).

As the vegetation progresses and especially after the plants are brought out into the open environment, the deviations related to the delay in their development and difficulty in feeding subside and do not prevent the occurrence of the next phases of all the plants and the completion of the cycle of the few control plants left after the mowing in each sample/pot.

Table 2. *Biometric and phytometric indicators of cultivated crops*

<i>Trifolium incarnatum</i> L.						<i>Flowers, Trifolium incarnatum</i> L.				<i>Medicago sativa</i> L.			
Fresh weight	Air-dry weight	Crop height/ flowering stage/ avg.	Number of blooms			Fresh weight	Air-dry weight	Weight ratio Flowers/Green mass	Fresh weight	Air-dry weight	Crop height/ early bud stage/ avg.		
g		cm	06.06. 2023	08.06. 2023	Sample No.	g		% / avg.	g		cm		
Point 1/Yana; Eutric Regosols (Toxic)													
1/1/TI	8.18	3.441	42	2	6	1/1/F	1.68	0.49	20.513	1/1/MS	25.4	8.8	40
1/2/TI	12.198	4.091	35	1	3	1/2/F	2.65	0.84	21.725	1/2/MS	24.2	7.9	38
1/3/TI	8.72	3.58	33	0	1	1/3/F	0.68	0.22	7.787	1/3/MS	22.6	6.8	37
									16.675				
Point 2/ Rudinata; Chromic-Calcaric Cambisols													
2/1/TI	137.26	19.799	63	27	33	2/1/F	27.94	6.35	20.358	2/1/MS	106.1	20.1	45
2/2/TI	145.53	21.485	68	22	36	2/2/F	26.44	5.54	18.169	2/2/MS	78.0	12.4	50
2/3/TI	146.47	21.338	65	22	32	2/3/F	26.79	6.16	18.292	2/3/MS	115.8	24.5	44
									18.940				
Point 3/ Seslavtsi; Rhodic Cambisols													
3/1/TI	199.1	28.671	69	12	22	3/1/F	29.06	5.74	14.598	3/1/MS	155.5	28.9	47
3/2/TI	210.71	31.31	74	10	24	3/2/F	26.70	4.44	12.670	3/2/MS	153.2	29.6	55
3/3/TI	272.74	43.175	71	13	22	3/3/F	34.98	7.01	12.827	3/3/MS	133.9	30.9	50
									13.365				
Point 4/ Kremikovtsi													
4/1/TI	35.328	9.476	35	3	11	4/1/F	4.28	1.65	12.124	4/1/MS	38.1	14.1	30
4/2/TI	50.964	15.647	48	0	8	4/2/F	6.70	2.61	13.147	4/2/MS	39.3	13.4	27
4/3/TI	39.283	11.641	43	0	5	4/3/F	5.15	1.89	13.102	4/3/MS	31.5	8.6	28
									12.791				

The bud stage of clover occurs around 25 - 28/05/2023, respectively earlier for Cambisols and later for Regosols and Fluvisols crops. Flowering occurs on 05/31/2023 for clover sown on Cambisols, on 06/03/2023 on Fluvisols and on 06/05/2023 on contaminated Regosols. In its mass stage, flowering everywhere occurs about two weeks later, when the vegetative trial with the harvest of both crops is completed, and as traced on the control plants left, the phase lasts on average over a month and a half. Alfalfa at the end of the experiment is still in the phase of formation of inflorescences and single (5 pcs.) flowering plants in the Cambisols - the crops (Figure 6).

Depending on the type of soil, the cultivated clover has some characteristic features:

In Cambisols crops, clover growing on carbonate dusty and sandy Chromic-Calcaric Cambisols is distinguished by more abundant flowering with large inflorescences (average, fresh weight 27.1 g from one pot), and low but more branched stems (and fertile branches) and correspondingly more leaf mass (average, fresh weight 143.1 g), compared to that of Rhodic Cambisols, where flowering plant individuals are fewer, plants are the tallest and weakly branched, but the crop as a whole for the experiment is the most abundant in green mass and color, respectively - average, fresh weight 227.5 g. and 30.2 g. (Table 1, Figure 6). It has been estimated

Figure 6. Crops grown in clover flowering phase. With a capital letter - alfalfa and clover, with a small letter - clover details. A, a - Regosols; B, b - Chromic-Calcaric Cambisol; C, c - Rhodic Cambisol; D, d - Fluvisols. B, b and C, c - 08/06/2023; A, a and D, d - 15/06/2023.

per pot. Clover grown on Regosols is distinguished by shorter stems, but with more leaf mass and larger flowers than those on Fluvisols - crops. For the Regosols, the weight of the flower was on average 16.7 % of the weight of the green mass, and for the Fluvisols, this percentage was the lowest for the whole experiment - 12.8 %. For the crops of Fluvisols, their numerous but small flowers and the least developed root system are their most distinctive features (Figure 6). The reason may again lie in the lower humus content of Fluvisols. Deteriorated soil structure and water permeability are not the determining factors, since in toxic Regosols these indicators are worse, and plants have more developed reproductive organs (flowers and seeds) and a root system with more lateral and fine branches to the main root, in compared to those of Fluvisols-crops.

The more branched and dense root system of the clover sown on the adjacent Points 1 and 2, respectively Regosols (arsenic-contaminated) and Chromic-Calcaric Cambisols (uncontaminated), was also accompanied by the presence of tubers of symbiotic nitrogen-fixing bacteria at various locations along the main root and branching, which are in equivalent amounts in contaminated and uncontaminated soils. Lumps from base to top and were also observed on the less branched main root of clovers grown on Rhodic Cambisols, but only single ones were found in the root system of Fluvisols crops.

Due to the highlighted observations, it can be concluded that the main factors limiting the fertility of crimson clover in the studied soil samples are the lower content of soil colloids (humus and clay) and the poor soil microbiota, and not the contamination with arsenic (and some heavy metals) (Regosols), the high carbonate content (Chromic-calcaric Cambisols), the high dust content (Chromic-calcaric Cambisols, Regosols) and the high seeding density (Rhodic Cambisols). Arsenic contamination, accompanied by reduced clay content, soil compaction and impaired water

that in clover yield from Chromic-Calcaric Cambisols the flower weight averages 18.9% of the green mass weight, while for Rhodic Cambisols this percentage is 13.4%. It was also observed that the root system of the former is more fragmented and rich in root hairs, compared to the clover of the humus-rich and best-structured Rhodic Cambisols, whose main root is the most powerful, poor in fine root hairs and overtakes the considerably few lateral roots. A reason for these morphological differences could be sought in the degree of germination and seeding density, which are lower in clover on Chromic-Calcaric Cambisols, and there the sparser seeding manages to receive more light and space for development.

The yield of clover was lowest in the toxic Regosols with an average fresh weight of the green mass of 9.7 g and 1.7 g of the flower. For clover grown on Fluvisols, these indicators are 41.9 g of green mass and 5.4 g of color, on average

permeability, has an impact in the initial phases of the vegetative cycle of crimson clover, expressed in poor germination and difficult nitrogen nutrition. The growth of the crop is also suppressed, but this does not affect its fertility and implementation of its main function - symbiotic association with nitrogen-fixing bacteria in its root system.

Alfalfa growth and development, with some deviations, followed the same trends as clover in the studied soil types (Figure 7). The main differences observed between the two crops were the

Figure 7. Comparison table with representative plants from each pot/sample (variant) of the two crops at the time of harvest.

lower yield (in three of the points) than the alfalfa (first swath) and the sparsely branched and root system consisting of a deep taproot, rarely branched, along which are single tubers of nitrogen-fixing bacteria. An exception is that in the toxic Regosols the yield of alfalfa was about three times higher, compared to that of clover, and the plants had better biometric indicators than those of the Fluvisols-alfalfa crops. However, more tubers of nitrogen-fixing bacteria were found everywhere in the clover root system than in the alfalfa crop. The development of alfalfa in Fluvisols is most difficult, where it is not delayed, but normal development and the achievement of optimal plant sizes are suppressed. This observation corresponds to some extent with the lower fertility of clover in these soils discussed above, originating from the lower humus and clay content and possibly the poorer soil microbiome.

In none of the variants of the study, alfalfa showed signs of nitrogen deficiency. However, it was observed that in the contaminated Regosols, in the initial vegetative phenophases, until the plants were brought outdoors, alfalfa stems and leaves in all three pots/samples were blue-green in color with a violet tint (Figure 4), a sign of deficiency of phosphorus food for plants in these soils (Stanchev et al., 1984). Despite this shortfall, alfalfa generated nearly three times more yield than alfalfa, suggesting a greater adaptability of the crop in the studied soil differences.

Some questions remain debatable and will be addressed in further publications and trials. On the one hand, to compare the extracted amount of arsenic from the two crops. The question of the influence of the two leguminous crops on the microbiological composition of

the specific soil differences, including the presence and development of arsenic-tolerant species of soil Rhizobium, which has been researched to contain symbiotic species of lentils and soybeans, which by different mechanisms, they tolerate and transform arsenic compounds in the soil and, despite them, support the development of host plants (Reichman, 2007, Laha et al., 2021). The probable presence and isolation of arsenic-transforming bacteria in contaminated soils and their interaction with the studied legumes and their symbiotic rhizobia is also a matter of important scientific and applied importance, relevant to the goals of successful and sustainable complex - microbiological and phytoremediation of arsenic-contaminated soils.

Conclusions

1. According to the vegetative experiment, the crimson clover (*Trifolium incarnatum L.*) is suitable for remediation and improvement of the agrochemical, biological, physical and physicochemical properties of arsenic-contaminated soils - Regosols, by forming a dense root system with a relative abundance of tubers of symbiotic nitrogen-fixing microorganisms in it, in conditions of interventional contents of arsenic, significant compaction and deteriorated water permeability of the soils.

2. Arsenic contamination (in association with a number of heavy metals) suppresses the germination of both crops - crimson clover and alfalfa, the vegetative phenophases, nutrition, growth and development of the clover, but not the fertility of the obtained harvest of the studied crops. The main factors limiting the fertility of the two crops in the experiment were the low content of soil colloids (humus and clay) and the poorer soil microbiome.

3. The growth and development of alfalfa in polluted Regosols is easier and gives a higher yield, compared to crimson clover, but the root system of the plants is less branched and with fewer tubers of rhizobia on them. The observed better adaptability in feeding alfalfa in contaminated soils allows this crop to be applied in longer-term remediation measures.

4. The annual vegetation cycle of crimson clover, the ability to adapt to polluted soils and to generate satisfactory yields of green mass and flowers, as well as the prominent and agronomically valuable property of enriching the soil with more symbiotic nitrogen-fixing bacteria and correspondingly increasing soil fertility for short period, are good reasons for this type of annual crop to find wide application, apart from for remediation purposes, also in green fertilization measures in Bulgarian sustainable agriculture.

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